

CLOUDSAFE: ENSURING GROUP DATA INTEGRITY WITHOUT CERTIFICATES

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ABSTRACT

Cloud storage service supplies people with an efficient method to share data within a group. The cloud server is not trustworthy, so lots of remote data possession checking (RDPC) protocols are proposed and thought to be an effective way to ensure the data integrity. However, most of RDPC protocols are based on the mechanism of traditional public key infrastructure (PKI), which has obvious security flaw and bears big burden of certificate management. To avoid this shortcoming, identity-based cryptography (IBC) is often chosen to be the basis of RDPC. Unfortunately, IBC has an inherent drawback of key escrow. To solve these problems, we utilize the technique of certificateless signature to present a new RDPC protocol for checking the integrity of data shared among a group. In our scheme, user's private key includes two parts: a partial key generated by the group manager and a secret value chosen by herself/himself. To ensure the right public keys are chosen during the data integrity checking, the public key of each user is associated with her unique identity, for example the name or telephone number. Thus, the certificate is not needed and the problem of key escrow is eliminated too. Meanwhile, the data

integrity can still be audited by public verifier without downloading the whole data. In addition, our scheme also supports efficient user revocation from the group. The security of our scheme is reduced to the assumptions of computational Diffie-Hellman (CDH) and discrete logarithm (DL). Experiment results exhibit that the new protocol is very efficient and feasible.

INTRODUCTION

Cloud storage service offers user an efficient way to share data and work as a team. Once someone of the team uploads a file to the server, other members are able to access and modify the file by Internet. Many real applications such as Dropbox for Business [1] and TortoiseSVN [2] are used in many companies for their staff to work together. The most important problem of such applications is whether the cloud server provider (CSP) can ensure the data to be kept intact [3]. In fact, the CSP is not fully trustworthy and the failure of software or hardware is inevitable in some way, so serious accidents of the data corruption may occur at any time. Therefore, the user needs to audit the CSP to confirm the data on the cloud server is original. To ensure the integrity of stored data, a great number of RDPC schemes are proposed [4-32]. In

these schemes, each data block generates an authentication tag which is bound with the block. By checking the correctness of the tags, the verifier is able to learn the status of the data. However, most of these schemes only focus on checking the integrity for personal data [4-21, 29-32], which is not valid under the situation of data shared in a group. When data is shared among multiple users, some new challenges appear which are not well solved in the RDPC schemes for personal data. For example, block tags may be generated by any group user, and different group user will output different tags even if the block is the same one. Moreover, when a group user updates a block, it should regenerate the tag again. When auditing the data integrity, all the authentication tags generated individually need to be aggregated and the information of all the generators for these tags will be involved in. It brings great complexity for the checking scheme. Furthermore, the group is dynamic, any group member may initiatively leave or be fired from the group at any time, so the user revocation is also an important problem that must be addressed. More specifically, once a user is revoked, he should not be allowed to access or modify the data and all his public/private keys are invalid. Under this situation, it is impossible to check the correctness of the tags made by revoked user. Thus, all the tags made by revoked user should be renewed by other normal user. The traditional method is to download the blocks signed by revoked user from the CSP, calculate the new tags and upload the new tags to the cloud again. It will increase heavy computation and communication cost for the normal user.

Therefore, this task should be performed by the CSP rather than the normal user. How to design an efficient and secure method to outsource the task is a challenge issue. Besides, public verification is an attractive feature of the data integrity checking work. That is, the integrity of shared data can be verified by not only the data owner but also everyone who is interested in the cloud data. It is very important for RDPC protocol to support public verification under current open environment. Until now, lots of schemes [22-28] have been presented for the integrity verification of data shared in group. However, most of existing RDPC schemes [22-26, 28] are based on PKI. Although PKI is widely used and occupies an important position in public key cryptography, there are still some security threats in it. For example, the security of PKI is based on the trustworthiness of certificate authority (CA), but it is not an easy work to ensure the trustworthiness of CA. Besides, the management of certificate such as distribution, storage, revocation and verification is also a big burden. To avoid these problems, some ID-based RDPC schemes [27, 28] are proposed. Unfortunately, ID-based RDPC schemes suffer from key escrow problem. Namely, the private key generator (PKG) generates all the private keys for the users. If PKG is untrusted, the scheme is not secure either. Thus, ID-based RDPC schemes may be restricted to small, closed settings. Compared with PKI and IBC, certificateless cryptography [33] solves the problems of certificate management and key escrow at the same time. To construct certificateless

RDPC scheme is a good method for cloud data integrity checking.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

Yang and Jia [13] introduced a linear index table to support data dynamic. Yan et al. [14] further optimized the implementation of linear index table and provided an efficient RDPC scheme. Feng et al. [15] presented a public remote integrity checking scheme, which could protect the user identity on file level to reduce the storage and communication cost.

Zhu et al. [16] provided a cooperative PDP scheme for the multi-cloud setting, in which the data blocks were stored on different cloud servers. To improve the security, Wang [17] proposed another identity-based PDP scheme for multi-cloud setting without certificate management. Recently, Wang et al. [18] presented an incentive and unconditionally anonymous identity-based public PDP scheme. In order to reduce the computation cost of data owner, Wang et al. [19] presented a proxy-oriented PDP scheme which moved the work of tag generation from data owner to proxy. To address the problem of key escrow and certificate management, two PDP scheme based on certificateless [20] and certificate-based cryptography [21] were proposed respectively.

All the schemes mentioned above focused on the integrity verification for personal data. In 2012, Wang et al. [22] proposed a protocol for checking the integrity of data shared in a group. They utilized the technique of group signature to generate each authentication tag so as to preserve the

tag generator's privacy. Wang et al. [23] proposed another PDP scheme for group data which supported the group user's joining and leaving. Based on broadcast encryption and group signature techniques, Liu et al. [24] provided a PDP scheme for group data. To improve the efficiency, Wang et al. [25] presented another scheme based on ring signature technique. However, these two schemes didn't solve the problem of user revocation. To address this issue, Wang et al. [26] used proxy re-signature technique to propose a new scheme with user revocation.

Yu et al. [27] presented a PDP scheme without paring, which also supported dynamic group. Yuan and Yu [28] proposed a PDP scheme based on polynomial-based authentication tags, which aimed to solve the problem of multi-user modification for blocks. All these schemes rely on traditional PKI mechanism which has security risk and big burden for certificate management. Besides, schemes of [27, 28] also suffer from the problem of key escrow. Thus, there still exists big limitation for the schemes to be used in real applications.

II. DISADVANTAGES

- 1) The system was not implemented Attribute Based Encryption Method which leads less security on outsourced data.
- 2) The system is less security due to lack of Attribute Based Encryption and there is no block verification.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In the proposed system, the system mainly focuses on the integrity checking for data shared within a group. Suppose there is a scenario that a software engineer starts an open source project and calls on volunteers from the world to join the project. They work as a temporary team. All the codes of the project are stored on certain cloud server so that all the team members upload and modify the source code by Internet.

The team may be very big, so it should be set up and managed efficiently. The volunteers may leave the team at any time, so the problem of user revocation from the team should be considered. The most important thing is that there need some way to guarantee the integrity of source codes on cloud sever.

Motivated by such requirement, the system proposes a new RDPC scheme for data shared in a group. Different from previous work, our scheme is based on the certificateless signature technique to avoid the problems of certificate management and key escrow. In our scheme, the group creator generates the partial key for each group user on behalf of key generation centre. Each user selects a secret value privately. The private key of each group user contains two parts: a partial key and a secret value. All the data blocks are signed by group user to get corresponding authentication tags.

During the data verification, all the tags are aggregated to decrease the computation and communication cost. Based on CDH and DL assumptions, we prove the security of our scheme. Besides, our scheme supports public verification and efficient user

revocation. We implement our scheme and perform some experiments. The experiment results indicate that our scheme has good efficiency.

ADVANTAGES

- 1) In the proposed scheme, the shared data is divided into many blocks and each block is attached with an authentication tag. Thus, the CSP stores all the blocks and the corresponding tags for cloud user.
- 2) The data verifier is a person who checks the integrity of the data on CSP. Due to the feature of public verification, anyone could be the verifier in our scheme.

IV. ARCHITECTURE DIAGRAM

V. CONCLUSION

In this project, we present a novel RDPC scheme for data outsourced on cloud server. Our scheme devotes to solve the integrity checking for the group data which is shared among many clients of a team. We utilize the idea of certificate less signature to generate all the block tags. Because each user of a group has both partial key and secret value, the problem of key escrow is eliminated in our scheme and the certificate

management in PKI does not exist. Besides, our scheme supports public verification, efficient user revocation multiuser data modification detailed description of the system model and security model of our scheme. At last, based on the CDH and DL assumption, we prove the security of our scheme. The experiment results show that our scheme has good efficiency

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